

PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH TO STUDENTS' ACTIVE PARTICIPATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of educational psychology in the professional activities of teachers, as well as pedagogical and psychological approaches to social and educational issues. It provides practical recommendations on the most common educational problems and their psychological solutions.

Introduction. Educational psychology studies the educational process and the psychological characteristics of students, teachers, and other subjects participating in it. This field helps to deeply analyze the processes of students' learning in educational institutions and plays a major role in increasing the effectiveness of education. The importance of educational psychology in improving student learning is very great, because psychological factors directly affect the success of the learning process¹. Educational psychology develops teaching methods by studying the psychological foundations of student learning. Psychological processes such as students' memory, attention, emotions, and motivation determine the effectiveness of the learning process. For example, in-depth knowledge of the impact of psychological states (such as stress or anxiety) on students' learning during their learning process helps teachers find new ways to teach them effectively. At the same time, motivation for the level of student learning is also important in educational psychology. Students learn effectively only when they are interested and satisfied in their learning. Motivation directs the learning process, accelerates it, and increases its effectiveness. According to psychological theories, students can have intrinsic motivation (self-development, goal achievement) and extrinsic motivation (grades, rewards). Their combination makes the learning process more effective. When assessing student learning, it is necessary to take into account individual differences. Because each student has his or her own individual psychological characteristics. Students' learning methods, abilities, tastes, concentration levels, and learning speeds differ from each other. Educational psychology helps to choose teaching methods that are suitable for each student, taking into account these individual differences². At the same time, the teacher must understand their psychological needs when working with students, which helps to ensure the success of the learning process.

Teachers should also pay more attention to the importance of self-awareness and self-regulation in the educational process. This is because self-awareness (metacognition) is another important component of educational psychology. When students are taught to analyze their learning methods and the learning process, to identify their strengths and weaknesses, they will learn more effectively. Self-awareness helps to manage the learning process, achieve their goals, and improve the quality of learning. At the same time, the psychological aspects of the relationship between teachers and students also have a high impact on the quality of the lesson. Positive communication between teachers and students also affects student learning.

Main part. Psychologically, it is very important for the teacher to behave, relate to students, understand their needs and help them in an appropriate way. The teacher's empathy, building trust and increasing motivation contribute to student learning. Stress and management strategies also significantly affect some students. Students often experience stress during the educational process. Stress can negatively affect the learning process. Educational psychology develops various strategies for managing student stress, such as time management, positive thinking, relaxation and study techniques. These methods are necessary for students to succeed in the educational process. The general aspects of education and psychology are closely related to each other and consider aspects aimed at improving student development, the educational process and the pedagogical approach of the teacher. Education supports the intellectual, emotional and social development of a person. In this process, students acquire new knowledge, develop skills, and learn social experiences. Psychology studies human development, in particular, their mental and emotional state, behavior, emotions, and consciousness. Psychology helps to understand the relationship between students and teachers in the educational process³. Effective communication between teachers and students is important in the educational process. The teacher must take into account the needs and interests of the student and adapt the education to them. Psychology helps to improve the communication between students and teachers by analyzing the psychological state of the student. This, in turn, increases the motivation of students and reduces stress. As we know, the purpose of education is to interest students in studying and motivate them to learn. In a good educational environment, students strive to achieve their goals. Psychology studies motivation processes and determines what psychological approaches should be used to help students succeed in the educational process. Each student is unique, and an individual approach to the educational process is important. This, in turn, requires taking into account the student's unique abilities, interests, and needs. Psychology helps to analyze students individually, understand their psychological state, and adapt education accordingly. This approach helps students learn effectively. Education helps develop social and emotional skills. Students learn to work with each other, work in a team, and manage emotional states. Psychology helps to determine how students develop emotionally, social relationships, and behavior. The importance of psychologists in education is enormous. They help to organize the educational process effectively and in accordance with the needs of students. The following is a brief overview of the important role and importance of psychologists in education. Psychologists analyze the emotional, mental, and social development of students. They assess students' psychological needs, self-esteem, stress levels, learning motivation, and other psychological factors. This helps teachers better understand how to help students and what methods to use.

Psychologists provide psychological support to students in educational institutions. This support helps students manage stress, increase emotional stability, and develop self-awareness and self-management skills. Psychologists provide individual or group counseling to help students solve their problems. Psychologists use various psychological methods to increase student motivation in the educational process. For example, they help select materials that will arouse students' interest, create opportunities for students to feel successful, and develop incentive systems. Increased motivation increases students' desire to learn. Psychologists teach teachers how to communicate effectively with students, understand their emotions, and treat them with respect. Understanding students and responding to their needs helps teachers become more effective. Psychologists pay special attention to the social and emotional development of students in education. They teach students how to work in groups, solve social problems, and build good relationships with others. This helps to make the educational process more effective and balanced. Psychologists help students develop self-awareness, emotional regulation, decision-making, and personal development skills. This helps students build self-confidence. Psychologists work with teachers and parents to help students with special needs (e.g., learning disabilities, autism, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder)⁴. They help develop instructional strategies that are tailored to the individual needs of students. Psychologists help prepare teachers to use psychological approaches, understand students' psychological states, and work with them. This helps teachers become more effective and efficient in their work. Psychologists identify psychological problems in students at an early stage in educational institutions and develop preventive measures for them. This, in turn, affects the future success of students. Psychologists play an important role in creating a positive psychological environment in an educational institution. They create the necessary conditions for students to feel safe and free in the institution. This, in turn, is an important basis for the development of students. The importance of psychologists in education is that they support the psychological and emotional development of students, provide effective approaches to teachers, and also help increase success in the educational process. The role of psychologists in the education system serves to increase the efficiency not only of students, but also of teachers and the entire educational institution. In conclusion, educational psychology is of great importance in improving student learning. Taking into account psychological factors, individually supporting students, and increasing motivation can significantly increase the efficiency of the educational process. Teachers can also make the learning process more successful by establishing proper communication with their students, managing stress, and developing self-awareness. The following tips should be given to students regarding the importance of educational psychology in student learning. High motivation is very important in the learning process. Try to use internal and external motivation. Clearly define your goals and try to increase motivation by celebrating small achievements on the way to their implementation. Self-development and enjoying learning new knowledge will lead you to success in the learning process. Self-awareness (metacognition) helps to improve the learning process. Analyze how you learn and which methods are effective. In this way, optimize your learning methods, identify your strengths and weaknesses in learning.

This will allow you to manage your learning process and be more productive. Stress management is very important in the learning process. When stress is high, the learning process

becomes difficult. To reduce stress, maintain a balance between rest and study, and calm your mind with meditation or exercise. In this way, you can reduce the stress of studying and achieve effective learning. Active learning methods are methods that do not just listen to or read information, but also apply it in practice, discuss it, or explain it to other students. These methods help to understand and remember information more deeply. For students, increasing activity in the learning process speeds up learning. Generally speaking, each student's learning method and pace are different. Find methods that allow for self-development by understanding your needs. If some aspects of learning are difficult, use additional resources, such as extracurricular activities, online courses, or asking for help from a teacher. Students should also be willing to change their study methods. Applying these recommendations in practice, based on the basic principles of educational psychology, will help students effectively and successfully complete the learning process. For students who have difficulty concentrating, psychologists can offer several methods of assistance 5. The following methods can help facilitate the learning process: Psychologists can introduce students to various exercises aimed at improving attention. For example, recommending short 5-10 minute exercises or online programs that help to concentrate. Study time for students should be clearly planned. Keeping study sessions short and effective, for example, studying for 20-30 minute intervals followed by a short break, can help. Create a quiet, orderly, and distraction-free learning environment. Techniques that help students focus, such as listening to music or using a light environment (such as blue lighting or soft background music), can be recommended. Setting goals for students, encouraging them, and celebrating successes in small steps can help improve self-motivation. These techniques encourage them to focus more on their studies. For students who have difficulty concentrating, psychologists can help them accept change and develop positive thinking. Instead of focusing on failures, teach them to appreciate small successes. Psychologists can teach cognitive techniques and study strategies that help improve attention. For example, time management using the "pomodoro technique," or focusing on pre-planned parts of their studies. If a student is experiencing stress or anxiety, psychologists can teach techniques to reduce stress and improve focus. For example, stress can be reduced through breathing exercises, meditation, or physical activity. Digital technologies can be used to help focus attention. For example, special study apps or programs (for attention management and task allocation) can help the student. Using these methods individually or in groups can be effective for students, and psychologists can adapt each of these methods to the needs of the students. In the course of further scientific work, it is necessary to study these topics in a wide range. In addition, there are situations when, even if the methodology and attitude of teachers comply with all psychological and pedagogical principles, problems with parents can negatively affect the learning of students. Psychologists have made many recommendations to improve the learning of such students.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that psychologists should understand the feelings of the student and have open conversations with them. Students should have the opportunity to express their feelings and problems. This will help reduce the student's stress and motivate them to be more attentive to their development. Students should be taught effective and respectful communication skills. Good communication with parents, teaching them to relieve emotions and deal with them positively, will help the student to develop.

Psychologists should teach students the skills necessary to manage stress, solve problems and deal with emotional conflicts. This includes breathing exercises, positive thinking and other stress reduction techniques. Problems with parents can lead to a student's low self-esteem. Psychologists should help students to increase their self-confidence and see positive changes. This will help the student feel better and find motivation for their academic success. Psychologists should explain to students the importance of studying to increase their motivation. Showing them the positive aspects of solving problems will increase the student's desire to achieve their goals. Psychologists should work in partnership with the student's parents. Organizing meetings with parents, informing them about their child's problems and teaching them ways to support them, will help solve the common problem. Psychologists should try to place the student in a safe and supportive learning environment. This will help the student feel free and comfortable, and thereby improve the student's concentration on studying. Students should be helped to strengthen social ties with friends and be active in group work. Positive relationships with others help the student feel confident and motivate them to achieve academic success. With the help of these recommendations, psychologists can help students overcome problems with parents and motivate them to improve their learning process. In addition, the following 10 psychological recommendations for increasing student learning efficiency can be given as recommendations for widespread application in practice:

Clearly setting goals Setting goals during the study process helps students to orient themselves. Setting small and large goals and making a plan to achieve them increases motivation to study.

Time management Study time should be planned. Effectively allocating time to complete a specific task within a certain time makes the learning process effective. This is useful when dividing time into parts and using the "Pomodoro" technique.

Developing Self-Confidence Students need to believe in themselves. Positive thoughts and increasing confidence in their own abilities will enable them to study effectively by overcoming stress and anxiety.

Stress Management Stress management is important during the study process. Reducing stress through breathing exercises, meditation, or short physical exercises will increase study efficiency.

Positive Thinking Positive thinking and self-motivation will facilitate the study process. Students should motivate themselves during the study process by telling themselves positive self-talk, such as "I can do this."

Taking Breaks Taking regular breaks while studying improves brain function. Using the "Pomodoro" technique or taking short breaks every 30-45 minutes is effective.

Creating a Good Study Environment Creating a calm, quiet, and organized environment for study is essential. Avoiding external noise, distractions from phones, and other factors will increase study efficiency.

Increase physical activity Regular physical exercise increases brain function and attention. Engaging in physical activity for 20-30 minutes every day helps improve study performance.

Optimize sleep Good sleep increases study performance. Students should focus on regular and sufficient sleep. Paying special attention to the quantity and quality of sleep improves cognitive functions.

Experimentation and learning from mistakes Learning from mistakes by their nature and learning from them increases study performance. Instead of accepting mistakes as failures, students should learn from them and try to improve. These recommendations will help students maximize their potential in the study process. Study performance can be increased through self-regulation, positive thinking, and effective strategies. In addition, this subject, which is currently introduced as a practical science in higher

education institutions to provide comprehensive guidance to young people, performs the following tasks: Optimization of the pedagogical process One of the main tasks of pedagogics is the effective organization of the educational process. This is the study of pedagogical methods, styles and techniques and their use in providing students with advanced knowledge. Development of educational activities pedagogics is aimed at developing not only knowledge, but also moral and spiritual values in students. Organizing educational activities, teaching moral values and developing personal responsibility are one of the practical tasks of pedagogics. Using an individual approach Taking into account the individual characteristics of students and using different methods depending on the capabilities of each student is an important task of pedagogics. This helps to develop the personal abilities of students. Increasing student motivation. pedagogics uses various pedagogical methods to increase students' interest in studying and learning. Motivating students, encouraging them to learn is one of the practical tasks of the discipline. Developing cooperation with society. Pedagogical education seeks to make the educational process more effective by bringing together teachers, parents of students and society. This helps to improve relations between school and society. Development of pedagogical technologies. Another practical task of the discipline of pedagogical education is the development of pedagogical technologies and their effective application in the educational process. These technologies help to improve the quality of education and implement innovative methods. Support for the psychological and emotional development of students. Pedagogical education studies the psychological and emotional state of students and helps them to study and actively participate in society. The use of various psychological methods is important for students to find their place in the social environment. Teacher training Pedagogical education helps teachers to improve their skills. This includes introducing teachers to new pedagogical methods and technologies, ensuring a more responsible approach to their work. Conducting pedagogical experiments Testing new methods and techniques, conducting experiments, and applying new knowledge and methods in practice are among the practical tasks of the discipline of pedagogics. Ensuring social integration of students Another practical task of pedagogics is ensuring social integration. Teaching students to be equal and active members of society and offering solutions to social problems is one of the goals of pedagogics. The practical tasks of pedagogics help to improve the quality of the educational process and form the knowledge and skills necessary for students to successfully live in society.

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